

On a possible approach to the Twin prime conjecture

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Abstract

We present an elementary approach that suggests a possible route toward addressing the Twin Prime Conjecture. The method relies on a commutative monoid under multiplication and counts the number of integers $\leq 6N + 1$ that are eliminated by the divisibility conditions using a sieve-type counting argument based on the inclusion–exclusion principle.

My idea is based on the fact that prime numbers greater than 3 appear only in $(6k-1)$, $(6k+1)$.

And the form of $(6k \pm 1)$ is closed under multiplication.

If any number in the sequence $(6k \pm 1)$ is not prime, it is only if it is the product of $(6k' \pm 1)$.

Ex)

$$\begin{aligned}25 &= 5 \times 5 \\25 &= 6 \times 4 + 1, 5 = 6 \times 1 - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}22295 &= 5 \times 7^3 \times 13 \\22295 &= 6 \times 3716 - 1 \\5 &= 6 \times 1 - 1, 7 = 6 \times 1 + 1, 13 = 6 \times 2 + 1\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, for a given parameter N , we can find the number of twin primes less than or equal to $(6N + 1)$.

Lemma1

All prime numbers greater than or equal to 5 can be expressed as two forms:

$$6k - 1$$
$$6k + 1$$

Pf)

All natural numbers are expressed by

$$6k, 6k+1, 6k+2, 6k+3, 6k+4, 6k+5$$

$6k$ is a multiple of 6.

$6k+2=2(3k+1)$ is a multiple of 2.

$6k+3=3(2k+1)$ is a multiple of 3.

$6k+4=2(3k+2)$ is a multiple of 2.

$6k+5=6(k+1)-1$ is the form of $(6k-1)$.

Therefore, the only two possible forms that could be prime are
 $(6k - 1), (6k + 1)$

For some natural number m , if $(6m-1)$ and $(6m+1)$ is all prime numbers at the same time, these two numbers are twin primes.

$$\text{Ex) } 11 = 6 \times 2 - 1, 13 = 6 \times 2 + 1$$

11,13 are twin primes.

Lemma2.

The product of $(6k - 1)$ or $(6k + 1)$ are again in the form of $(6k' - 1)$ or $(6k' + 1)$

pf)

(i)

$$\begin{aligned}(6k - 1) \times (6m - 1) &= 36km - 6k - 6m + 1 \\ &= 6(6km - k - m) + 1 = 6k' + 1\end{aligned}$$

(ii)

$$\begin{aligned}(6k - 1) \times (6m + 1) &= 36km + 6k - 6m - 1 \\ &= 6(6km + k - m) - 1 = 6k' - 1\end{aligned}$$

(iii)

$$\begin{aligned}(6k + 1) \times (6m - 1) &= 36km - 6k + 6m - 1 \\ &= 6(6km - k + m) - 1 = 6k' - 1\end{aligned}$$

(iv)

$$\begin{aligned}(6k + 1) \times (6m + 1) &= 36km + 6k + 6m + 1 \\ &= 6(6km + k + m) + 1 = 6k' + 1\end{aligned}$$

It can be inductively proven that no matter how many times this form is multiplied, it will take the same form again.

Define {younger brother set}, and {older brother set}

Younger brother set $Y = \{k \in \mathbb{N} \mid 6k - 1\}$

That is,

Younger brother set=
 $\{5, 11, 17, 23, 29, 35, 41, 47, 53, 59, 65 \dots\}$

Older brother set $O = \{k \in \mathbb{N} \mid 6k + 1\}$

That is,

Older brother set=
 $\{7, 13, 19, 25, 31, 37, 43, 49, 55, 61, 67 \dots\}$

Consider the union of these two sets

$$U = \{Y \cup O\}$$

By Lemma1 and Lemma2, If you multiply any elements of a set U, it will belong to U again.

This set forms a commutative monoid under multiplication.

In other words, the elements of set U are a candidates that could become twin prime numbers.

Let any element of $U = u_i$

If u_i is excluded from the prime number, the reason is that

$$u_i = u_j \times u_k$$

For example,

$$55 = 5 \times 11$$

And 5,11 are the elements of U . And also 55 is a element of U .

$$55 = 6 \times 9 + 1$$

Therefore,

$$53 = 6 \times 9 - 1$$

53, 55 are eliminated from twin prime numbers.

We can find patterns of elimination.

Let

Twin Field: a field in which the elements of set U are stretched out

(i) Elimination by 5

Consider

$$5 \times \text{set } Y$$

That is,

$$\begin{aligned} &5 \times \{5, 11, 13, 23 \dots\} \\ &= 25, 55, 85, 115 \dots \end{aligned}$$

We can find pattern. There's always difference of 30.

And observe that the parameters of Twin Field, k .

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &= 6 \times 4 + 1 \\ 55 &= 6 \times 9 + 1 \\ 85 &= 6 \times 14 + 1 \\ 115 &= 6 \times 19 + 1 \\ &\vdots \end{aligned}$$

All of these are in the form of $(6k + 1)$

And we focus on the parameters k .

$$k = 4, 9, 14, 19 \dots$$

It looks the form of

$$k = 5m - 1$$

How can we prove it?

$$5 \times (6m - 1) = 30m - 5$$

$$= 30m - 6 + 1 = 6(5m - 1) + 1$$

Therefore, in the form

$$5 \times (6m - 1) = 6k + 1 \text{ (by lemma2)}$$

$$6k + 1 = 6 \times (5m - 1) + 1,$$

$$k = 5m - 1$$

k is the parameter of the twin field, so all numbers corresponding to

$$k = 5m - 1$$

are excluded from the twin primes.

(ii)

$$5 \times \text{set } 0$$

$$5 \times (6m + 1) = 30m + 5 = 30m + 6 - 1 = 6(5m + 1) - 1$$

Therefore, in the form

$$6k - 1 = 6 \times (5m + 1) - 1$$

$$k = 5m + 1$$

All parameter numbers corresponding to

$$k = 5m + 1$$

are excluded from the twin primes.

Combining (i) and (ii),

For the parameter of Twin field, k ,

$$k = 5m \pm 1$$

Are excluded from the twin primes.

Similar patterns can be found in the elements of set U as well, not just 5.

$$7 \times (6m - 1) = 42m - 7 = 42m - 6 - 1 = 6(7m - 1) - 1$$

$$k_1 = 7m - 1$$

$$7 \times (6m + 1) = 42m + 7 = 42m + 6 + 1 = 6(7m + 1) - 1$$

$$k_2 = 7m + 1$$

Combining k_1, k_2 ,

$$k = 7m \pm 1$$

Are excluded from the twin primes.

Generalization

Elements of $Y = (6n-1)$ (fixed)

Product to elements of $Y=(6m-1)$

$$\begin{aligned}(6n - 1) \times (6m - 1) &= 6(6nm - m) - 6n + 1 \\ &= 6(6nm - n - m) + 1 = 6\{m(6n - 1) - n\} + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$k_1 = (6n - 1)m - n$$

Elements of $Y=(6n-1)$ (fixed)

Product to elements of $O=6m+1$

$$\begin{aligned}(6n - 1) \times (6m + 1) &= 36nm + 6n - 6m - 1 \\ &= 6(6nm + n - m) - 1 = 6\{m(6n - 1) + n\} - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$k_2 = (6n - 1)m + n$$

Combining k_1, k_2

$$k = (6n - 1)m \pm n$$

For example, $17 = 6 \times 3 - 1$

Elements of the Twin Field eliminated by 17

$$k = 17m \pm 3$$

Elements of set $O = (6n+1)$ (fixed)

Product to elements of $Y = (6m-1)$

$$\begin{aligned}(6n + 1) \times (6m - 1) &= 36nm - 6n + 6m - 1 \\ &= 6(6nm - n + m) - 1 = 6\{m(6n + 1) - n\} - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$k_1 = (6n + 1)m - n$$

Elements of set $O = (6n+1)$ (fixed)

Product to elements of set $O = (6m+1)$

$$\begin{aligned}(6n + 1) \times (6m + 1) &= 36nm + 6n + 6m + 1 \\ &= 6(6nm + n + m) + 1 = 6 \times \{m(6n + 1) + n\} + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$k_2 = (6n + 1)m + n$$

Combining k_1, k_2

$$k = (6n + 1)m \pm n$$

EX) $31 = 6 \times 5 + 1$

Elements of the Twin Field that eliminated by 31

$$k = 31m \pm 5$$

In summary,

k=1	5 7
k=2	11 13
k=3	17 19
k=4	23 25
k=5	29 31
k=6	35 37
k=7	41 43
k=8	47 49
k=9	53 55
k=10	59 61

⋮

$k = 5m \pm 1 = 4, 6, 9, 11 \dots$ *exclude*.

Denote this sequence $\rho(5)$

$k = 7m \pm 1 = 6, 8, 13, 15 \dots$ *exclude*. $\rho(7)$

$k = 11m \pm 2 = 9, 13, 20, 24 \dots$ *exclude* $\rho(11)$

$k = 13m \pm 2 = 11, 15, 24, 26 \dots$ *exclude* $\rho(13)$

⋮

Therefore this is the question.

These sequences $\rho(5), \rho(7), \rho(11), \rho(13) \dots$ can exclude all k , the parameter of the Twin Field?

However, there are duplicate numbers in these sequences.

But we ignore it and let's find the minimum remaining ratio.

$\rho(5)$: period 5, 2 exclude \rightarrow The average remaining proportion among k up to N is

$$\frac{3}{5} N$$

$\rho(7)$: period 7, 2 exclude. Average remaining proportion $\frac{5}{7}$

$\rho(11)$: period 11, 2 edclude. Average remaining proportion $\frac{9}{11}$

\vdots

The approximate remaining ratio:

$$\frac{3}{5} \times \frac{5}{7} \times \frac{9}{11} \times \frac{11}{13} \times \frac{15}{17} \times \frac{17}{19} \times \frac{21}{23} \times \frac{23}{25} \times \frac{27}{29} \times \frac{29}{31} \times \dots$$

We can simplify it and if the number of twin primes is finite, this minimum must be diverge to finite number.

Then, we have to notice two facts:

1. For some natural number q ,

Too big number q cannot exclude the number k less than or equal to N .

For example,

$$\rho(11) = 11m \pm 2 = 9, 13, 20, 24 \dots$$

Since m is a natural numbers,

$\rho(11)$ cannot exclude the number k which is less than 9.

$$\rho(25) = 25m \pm 4 = 21, 29, 46, 54 \dots$$

$\rho(25)$ cannot exclude the number k which is less than 21.

Therefore if we examine the natural numbers k less than 21, we don't need to product ratio $\rho(q)$, which is $q > 25$.

2.

$$7 \times 13 = 13 \times 7 = 91 = 6 \times 15 + 1$$

Product of 7 and 13 is equal to product of 13 and 7.

Therefore, if we examine until $k \leq 15$,

we don't need to product the ratio of $\rho(13)$.

Because it is already eliminated by 5,7, which is the Twin Field number less than 13.

In general, if we examine the exclude Twin Field number k up to N ,

It is sufficient to product the ratio $\rho(q)$ which satisfies

$$q \leq \sqrt{6N + 1}$$

Now, use this fact, if we calculate the average number of k up to N that will not be eliminated, for $q \leq \sqrt{6N + 1}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{average} &= N \times \frac{3}{5} \times \frac{5}{7} \times \frac{9}{11} \times \frac{11}{13} \times \frac{15}{17} \times \dots \times \frac{q-2}{q} > N \times \frac{3}{q} \\ &\geq N \times \frac{3}{\sqrt{6N+1}} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the average number of k which is not eliminated is greater than $\frac{3N}{\sqrt{6N+1}}$ for all N .

If the number of twin primes is finite,

$$\frac{3N}{\sqrt{6N+1}}$$

must diverge (even if it is average) to a finite number as the value of N increases. Why? Even if it remains less than the average in certain sections, the other section remains more. Because it is 'average' for infinite scale.

But

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \text{infinite}} \frac{3N}{\sqrt{6N+1}} = \text{infinite}$$

number of twin primes is not finite as N increases.

If we assume that twin primes is finite, it is contradiction.

As a result, the number of twin primes is infinite.

Plus)

Why 'not eliminated k' is always prime number?

Because if any composite number S is factorized, it is always factorized by prime number.

And prime number is 2,3,5,7...

All prime numbers except 2,3 are always on the Twin Field.

And any $(6k-1)$ and $(6k+1)$ are not a multiple of 2 or 3.

And Twin Field is closed under product.

Therefore, if any number on the Twin Field is a composite number, it is always factorized into elements of Twin Field.

And a product of Twin Field is always on the sequence

$$\rho(5), \rho(7), \rho(11), \rho(13) \dots$$

So any 'not eliminated k' is always make twin primes

$$(6k - 1), (6k + 1)$$

References:

[1] G.H. Hardy and E.M. Wright, *An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers*, 6th ed., Oxford Univ. Press, 2008.